

ESTIMATION OF ACTIVE CLAY CONTENT USING ATTERBERG LIMITS PARAMETERS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents models that estimate the active clay content of the soil based on the correlation between the ratio of the second and first norm of the idealized fall cone curve (distance factor) and the arithmetic difference between the plasticity index and the clay content (clay index). The models were developed based on an analysis of 306 test results of clay content and Atterberg limits collected from the literature. The models were found to compute the active clay limit reasonably well, with most of the calculated results falling within the statistical testing bound of ± 12 as provided in AASHTO T88-10.

INTRODUCTION

Based on BS 1377 and AASHTO T88-10, soil particles with a diameter of less than 0.002 mm are classified as clay. Therefore, these standard procedures determine total clay content, including active (cohesive) and inactive (cohesionless) clay. In accordance with the definition of clay, a finely-grounded, non-plastic cohesionless rock flour, a non-clay mineral, is classified as clay if its particles are smaller than 0.002 mm. The inability of the methods of determining clay content to discern active and inactive clay makes the methods less useful in practice. The reproducibility of clay content determination is 12%, according to AASHTO T88-10.

The plasticity is imparted to the soil by active clay. Therefore, the amount of active clay within the soil matrix must be correlated to the plasticity index. Maregesi(2023) showed that inactive and active clay are delineated by the arithmetic difference between the plasticity index and clay content (PI-clay). The word clay index is coined to define this arithmetic difference between the plasticity index and clay content. Models that can be used to estimate the clay content were proposed using a correlation between the clay index and the average fall cone slope (20/LL). Clay whose clay index is

equal to or more than zero predominantly contains active clay and is correlated to the plasticity index and liquid limit. Soils whose clay index is less than zero are predominantly inactive clay with a small amount of active clay, which imparts plasticity to the soil and is not correlated to the liquid limit and plasticity index.

The inclusion of both inactive and active clay during the determination of the clay content makes the correlation between the plasticity index and clay content challenging or impossible to model mathematically. The presence of inactive clay in total clay content distorts the correlation between clay content and the plasticity index. However, if the inactive clay content is separated from the active clay content, it is possible to mathematically model the relationship between the plasticity index and clay content (Maregesi, 2023). Therefore, any model that can be used to predict the plasticity index can also be used to predict the amount of active clay within the soil matrix.

Based on the premise that any model that can be used to estimate the plasticity index can be used to estimate the amount of active clay within the soil matrix, this paper presents a model that estimates the active clay content using the ratio of the first and second norm of the idealized fall cone curve as defined in equation (1). The word distance factor (D_f) is coined to define this ratio. The distance factor can be used to compute the plasticity index of the soil (Maregesi, 2023).

A total of 306 Atterberg limits and clay content test results collected from the literature were analyzed, and 172 selected test results whose clay index was more than zero were used to develop models of computing the active clay content. The data analyzed during this study were collected from the following listed literature:- (Reddy et al. (2020) -45 test results, Cerato et al. (2006) -4 test results, Prakash et al. (2012) – 9 test results, Sridharan et al.,(2000) – 4 test results, Vincent et al. (2021) -6 test results, Otoko (2014)- 12 test results, Widjaja

et al. (2020)- 21 test results, Sridharan et al. (1986)-7 test results, Spagnoli et al. (2018) – 76 test results, Afolagboye et al. (2021) – 75 test results, Karakan (2020)- 34 test results, Mishra et al (2012) – 13 test results, Sridharan et al (1988) – 5 test results and Reznik (2016)- 5 test results.

$$D_f = \frac{||L||_2}{||L||_1} = \frac{\sqrt{LL^2 + 20^2}}{LL + 20} \dots \dots (1)$$

Where,

D_f is the distance factor, LL is the liquid limit, $||L_2||$ is the second norm (euclidian distance), and $||L_1||$ is the first norm (Manhattan distance).

THE ATTERBERG LIMITS AND CLAY CONTENT

Figure 1 shows the variation in plasticity index and clay content. It is evident that as the clay content increases, the plasticity index also increases. However, due to the scattering of the test results, it is impossible to establish a good correlation that can be used to compute the clay content directly from the plasticity index, as evidenced by the coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.5164 when the data is fitted using the logarithmic model shown in equation 2.

Furthermore, it can be seen that there is a linear correlation between the plasticity index and clay content for soil with a plasticity index of not more than 100 and clay content of less than 60 (Figure 2). For soils with plasticity index values of more than 100 and clay content exceeding 60, the clay content and plasticity index are non-linearly correlated (Figure 1). It is worth mentioning that most of the test results in Figures 1 and 2 plots within the statistical testing bound of ± 12 as provided in AASHTO T88-10, suggesting a correlation between the plasticity index and the clay content.

DEVELOPMENT OF MODEL OF COMPUTING ACTIVE CLAY CONTENT

Casagrande cup and fall cone methods of determining the liquid limits give different values of liquid limit; thus, the computed plasticity index also differs. However, in this study, it has been assumed that both methods yield the same results.

Figure 1: The variation between the plasticity index and clay content ($R^2=0.5164$)

$$clay = -23.558 + 18.0425 \ln(PI) \dots \dots (2)$$

Figure 2: Variation between the plasticity index and clay content

Maregesi (2023) showed that the ratio of the second norm(Euclidian norm) to the first norm(Manhattan distance) (Distance Factor, D_f) is highly correlated to the plasticity index of the soil. Figure 3 shows the correlation between the distance

factor and the plasticity index for the data analyzed during this study, from which it can be seen that they are highly correlated, as evidenced by the achieved coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.9978 when fitted with the rational function shown as equation 3.

Based on the data presented in Figure 3, it is evident that the distance factor can be used to estimate the plasticity index of the soil. Since the distance factor is highly correlated to the plasticity index, it must also be correlated to the clay index since the plasticity is imparted to the soil by active clay within the soil matrix.

Figure 3: The correlation between the distance factor and the plasticity index ($R^2=0.9978$)

$$PI = \frac{9.8393D_f - 5.3742}{1 - 1.7847D_f + 0.7846D_f^2} \dots (3)$$

Where

PI is the plasticity index, D_f is the distance factor

Figure 4 shows that the distance factor is correlated to the clay index. The data are fitted using the rational function shown in equation 4 with a coefficient of determination of 0.9698, suggesting that the model can be used to compute the clay content of the soil. However, a close examination of Figure 4 reveals that the distance factor and the clay index correlate up to zero clay index. There is no correlation between the distance factor and clay index for soil whose clay index is less than zero, as

evidenced in Figure 5. Figure 6 shows the correlation between the distance factor and clay index fitted with a rational equation as the best-fit curve with a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.993. The same type of correlation was observed when the average fall cone slope was correlated to the clay index (Maregesi, 2023).

Figure 4: The correlation between distance factor and clay index ($R^2=0.9698$)

Based on the analysis of the correlation between the average fall cone slope and clay index (Maregesi, 2023), as well as the correlation between the distance factor and the clay index, as shown in Figures 5 and 6, it is hypothesized that the active and inactive clay is delineated with a line which the clay index is zero ($PI-Clay=0$). The soil with a clay index of less than zero contains a substantial amount of inactive (cohesionless) clay such that clay activity is diluted, thereby distorting the correlation between clay content and plasticity index.

The soil, with a clay index of -100, is a non-clay mineral, cohesionless finely grounded particles of less than 0.002 mm in diameter, and the activity of this clay is zero. The clay with an activity of -99 is the clay whose active clay content is only 1%, and the remaining clay is inactive, and its activity can be interpreted as clay with an activity of 0.01. Equally, the soil with a clay index of -50 is interpreted as clay with activity of 0.5, implying that 50% of clay is

inactive while the remaining 50 is active clay content; in other words, you need 2% of clay in the soil to impart one unit of the plasticity to the soil. Finally, the soil with a clay index of 0 is interpreted as clay content with an activity of 1, implying that 1% of clay imparts one unit of plasticity to the soil. Therefore, it is postulated that the clay is active only when its clay index equals or exceeds zero. In other words, the clay is active when and only when its plasticity index is equal to or more than its clay content. Therefore, the active clay can be defined as the one whose inclusion of 1% within the soil matrix imparts at least one unit of plasticity index to the soil. This proposed definition agrees with the fact that since plasticity is imparted to the soil by the active clay, the plasticity index must also be correlated to the active clay content, as evidenced in Figures 6, 11, 12, and 13.

Soil with a clay index of more than zero contains a substantial amount of active clay such that the inclusion of one percent of active clay within the soil matrix is associated with the impartation of at least one unit of plasticity to the soil and the clay content is correlated to the plasticity index.

$$PI - Clay = \frac{8.1792D_f - 6.7353}{1 - 1.9756D_f + 0.9764D_f^2} \dots (4)$$

Figure 5: Variation of the distance factor and clay index of less than zero

Figure 6 shows the correlation between the distance factor and clay index ≥ 0 , from which it can be seen that the correlation is very good as fitted with rational function with a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.993, which suggests that the fit is quite good and the model can be used for computing active clay content within the soil matrix. The fitted equation is shown as equation 5. The correlation shown in Figure 6 supports the proposed postulation that the active clay content is correlated to the plasticity index. In contrast, Figure 5 supports the postulation that soil whose clay index is less than zero is not correlated to the plasticity index.

Figure 6: Correlation between the distance factor and $PI - Clay \geq 0$ ($R^2=0.993$)

$$PI - Clay = \frac{2.5561D_f - 1.7151}{1 - 2.0015D_f + 1.0022D_f^2} \dots (5)$$

Making clay the subject, equation 5 is transformed into equation 6.

$$Clay = PI - \left(\frac{2.5561D_f - 1.7151}{1 - 2.0015D_f + 1.0022D_f^2} \right) \dots (6)$$

Based on the achieved coefficient of determination of 0.993 for the data in Figure 6 warrants the use of equation 6 in the computation of the active clay content within the soil matrix using distance factor and plasticity index as predictor variables. Equation 1 can be substituted in equation 6, thus replacing

the distance factor such that the clay content can be computed using the plasticity index and liquid limit. Furthermore, equation 3 can substitute the plasticity index in equation 6, so the clay content can only be calculated using the liquid limit. However, this substitution makes the resulting equation too long and difficult to solve. Therefore, it is a straightforward operation to use Equation 1 and Equation 6 in the computation of the active clay content.

COMPUTATION OF THE ACTIVE CLAY CONTENT

The clay content of all soil with a clay index ≥ 0 was calculated to check the accuracy of the proposed model. The residual plot is shown in Figures 7 and 8, from which it can be seen that the proposed model predicts the clay content reasonably well, with 141 (82%) of 172 of the test results plotting within the statistical testing bound of ± 12 given in AASHTO T 88.

Figure 7: Residual plot showing the difference between the determined and computed clay

Based on the analysis of the residual, as shown in Figures 7 and 8, it is clear that the proposed model can be used to estimate the clay content for the soil with a clay index ≥ 0 . The model can be used to compute the equivalent active clay content, which imparts plasticity to the soil for the soil whose clay index is less than 0. Therefore, using this model, it

is possible to disaggregate the inactive clay from the active clay.

Figure 8: comparison between the determined and computed clay content

Figure 9: Residual histogram

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ACTIVE CLAY CONTENT AND ATTERBERG LIMITS

Figure 10 shows the correlation between the liquid limit and the active clay content. The data includes computed active clay content using equation 6 and

determined clay content. It can be seen that there is a good correlation between the liquid limit and the active clay content, as evidenced by the achieved coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.8507 when fitted using a logarithmic model shown in equation 7.

Furthermore, it can be seen that within the range of clay content of 60 and liquid limit of about 100, there is a linear correlation between the liquid limit and the clay content, suggesting that a simple linear relationship can be used to model the data within this range as evidenced in Figure 11. The fitted linear correlation achieved a coefficient of determination of 0.9011, suggesting that the linear model fits the liquid limit and the clay content reasonably well. It can be seen that 225(91%) of the 246 test results plots within the statistical testing bound of ± 12 . The fitted linear equation is shown as equation 8, which closely matches the previously presented equation by Maregesi (2023) of $clay = 0.4227LL$.

$$clay = 29.3907 \ln(LL) - 94.5762 \dots (7)$$

$$clay = 0.3804LL \dots (8)$$

Figure 10: The relationship between the liquid limit and active clay content (determined and computed clay content) ($R^2=0.9011$)

Figure 11: The relationship between the liquid limit and active clay content (determined and computed active clay content) ($R^2=0.9011$)

Figure 12 shows a correlation between the plasticity index and active clay content (computed and determined). It can be seen that the data are very well correlated, as evidenced by the rational best-fit curve fitted with the coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.8959, shown in equation 9.

As for the liquid limit, it can be seen that within the range of a plasticity index of 100 and clay content of 60, the plastic index is linearly correlated to the clay content with a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.9619. Based on the coefficient of determination assessment, the plasticity index is a better model for predicting the clay content. Therefore, the plasticity index predicts the clay content better than the liquid limit using a simple linear model with the limitation that the plasticity index must not exceed 100. The correlation between the plasticity index and active clay content is shown in Figure 13, along with the best-fit linear curve. The fitted linear equation model for computing the active clay content is shown in Equation 10. The resulting equation is statistically the same as the equation reported by Maregesi (2023) of $clay = 0.7622PI$. It can be seen that the model predicts the clay content using the plasticity index as the sole predictor variable. The model is very accurate because 247 (97%) out of the 255 results plotted within the statistical testing bound of $\pm 12\%$.

$$clay = \frac{107.0538PI}{99.748 + PI} \dots (9)$$

$$Clay = 0.7534PI \dots (10)$$

Figure 12: the relationship between the plasticity index and active clay content (computed and determined active clay content ($R^2=0.8959$))

Figure 13: The relationship between the plasticity index and active clay content (computed and determined, $R^2=0.9619$)

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis of 306 clay content and Atterberg limits test results collected from thirteen different authors, soils from various geographical locations, and of different geological origins, it has been shown that the clay index is the parameter that delineates the activeness of the clay minerals. The soil with a clay index of less than zero contains a substantial amount of inactive clay to the extent that it distorts the correlation between the clay content and the plasticity index. This soil contains a small amount of active clay that imparts plasticity to the soil. The activeness of the clay is diluted by the presence of the inactive clay within the soil matrix; as a result, the ability of the clay to impart plasticity to the soil is reduced to less than one unit of plasticity per one percent clay inclusion within the soil matrix. Therefore, soil with a clay index of less than zero can be classified as inactive clay.

The impartation of the plasticity index on the soil increases as the clay index increases. When the clay index is equal to zero, i.e., when the clay content is equal to the plasticity index of the soil (when the clay activity is one), then the clay content is fully active and contributes fully to the impartation of plasticity to the soil. Therefore, soil with a clay index of more than zero can be classified as active clay.

The clay index is correlated to the distance factor. This correlation can be used to compute the clay content for the soil with a clay index of more than zero. Still, it can also be used to compute the equivalent active clay content within the soil matrix for soil whose clay index is less than zero such that the inactive clay content can be discerned from the active clay content.

The clay content is linearly correlated to both the liquid limit and plasticity index for soil with a liquid limit or plasticity index of less than 100 and clay content of less than 60. Therefore, the clay content can be estimated using liquid limit or plasticity index for most of the soils. The linear model of estimating the clay from the plasticity index is more accurate for estimating the active clay content than the linear model, which utilizes the liquid limit to predict the active clay content.

The models of estimating the clay content proposed during this study can be used to estimate the clay

content for soils with a clay index that is equal to or more than zero. For soil whose clay index is less than zero, the models can be used to estimate the equivalent clay content, which imparts plasticity to the soil; thus, using the models proposed, the inactive clay can be discerned from the active clay.

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